

An Exploratory Study of Substance Use among Adolescent Nigerian Students: Association with Bullying and Social Support

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Abstract

Recent reports show that bullying has persisted in Nigerian public schools. Cases that have attracted public attention were mostly those that resulted in death, but bullying may yield other seemingly benign but grave outcomes such as substance use in attempt to grapple with such personally overwhelming situations. Social support is expected to attenuate such extreme measures. Early onset of substance use has been linked with profound health challenges and adjustment problems later in life. Applying a cross-sectional design, the present study investigated whether bullying and social support were associated with substance use in a sample of 375 students aged 11-19 years who were selected from three public secondary schools in Abakaliki. Participants completed the Psychoactive Substance Use Questionnaire, Forms of Bullying Scale, Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social support, and provided demographic data. The mean score of 5.95 (SD = 6.02) indicated the use of substances among the students. Regression results showed that being bullied was positively associated with substance use and that being a perpetrator of bullying was also positively but marginally associated with substance use. Friends support but not family or significant other support was negatively associated with substance use. We consider that intervention programme that controls bullying in schools may also contribute to reduction of substance use among students.

Keywords: Adolescent students, bullying, social support, substance use

Introduction

Adolescent substance use is a significant public health concern in Nigeria, frequently leading to substance abuse and misuse. It is particularly problematic because it can interfere with crucial social and developmental milestones. Early intervention is critical due to the potential for long-term negative impacts (Egwu, et al., 2024). Addressing this issue requires comprehensive social strategies. Adolescents who drink alcohol are more likely to experience negative consequences such as injury or death, difficulty at school, addiction, and legal problems and additionally, alcohol can interfere with brain development (NIDA, 2020). The World Health Organization notes that early onset of substance use is associated with higher risks of developing dependence and other problems during adult life, and younger people are disproportionately affected by substance use compared with older people (WHO, 2023). Studies in Nigeria documented its prevalence among adolescents, in the Southeast, for example, the prevalence rate of substance use among high school students was 32.9%, with alcohol being the most often used substance (29.0% users) and cocaine being the least (2.1%) (NSDU, 2018; Manyike et al., 2016). In the Southwest, adolescents reported using psychoactive drugs varies from 15.0% to 69.3%, particularly when native psychoactive drugs like kola nut were included (NSDU, 2018; Manyike et al., 2016). Alcohol remained the most often used substance, followed by cigarettes (Mefoh et al., 2018). Adolescents' substance use is attributed to various social factors and having bullying as one among them call for a need to understand bullying as being associated with substance use. The fact that adolescents is a stage where increase shift from parents to peers are more to compare to other stage of life result to diminished parental influence and increased peers' influence. The incidental increase in peers influence exacerbate bullying behaviour and disposition for perpetrator attack among them. This phenomenon is sine quo non in this stage and has become endemic in secondary schools. Researchers on peer bullying reportedly found that it is an alarming situation found common among this group at this stage of life (Bichi et al., 2025; Nwala, 2025).

Bullying particularly, is a social behaviour characterized by contextual attack to the weaker ones which occur among two or more individuals exercising power imbalance. It severely impacts physical, social and psychological health of the bullied individual (Mullan et al., 2023; Ojelade et al., 2025). There is enough evidence suggesting that bullying is a pervasive, humiliating experience affecting individuals globally, regardless of age or gender (Bichi et al., 2025; Nwala, 2025; Obioha et al., 2024; Ogunode et al., 2025). However, victims report severe emotional and physical consequences, including disturbances, bedwetting, headaches, stomach aches, and sadness (Mendy, et al., 2025; Ojelade et al., 2025). Peer bullying is a pervasive problem in schools with adverse implications for students, particularly during early adolescence stage (Owusu et al., 2011).

Literature review supported the notion that bullying is associated with substance use. A study on the association between bullying experience (as victims, bullies, or bystanders) and substance use conducted by Gaete, et al. (2017) found that bullies and bully-victims have a high risk for cigarette, alcohol, and cannabis use than bystanders. Airagnes et al. (2023) found that students who experienced higher levels of bullying indicated increased alcohol consumption. Tarafa et al. (2022) found that the prevalence of bullying victimisation was 30.4% and that being male, experiencing physical or emotional abuse, current substance use, and psychological distress were significantly associated with bullying victimisation. Pichel et al. (2022) found that adolescents involved in school bullying or cyberbullying, either as victims, perpetrators, or bully-victims, exhibited significantly higher rates of substance use and risky consumption patterns. Arcadepani et al. (2021) found a significant correlation between bullying perpetration and substance use among children and adolescents. Specifically, the results indicate that adolescents who engage in bullying behaviours are more likely to use alcohol, tobacco, and illicit drugs. Jiexin

and Zigiang (2024) found that experience with school bullying involvement emerged as a significant factor influencing more substance use (cigarettes, alcohol, and cannabis).

Social support is a variable expected to attenuate the association of bullying and substance use. This is because adolescents with higher perceived social support might be less likely to use substances, even if they experience peer bullying. Few literatures accounted for this attenuate expectation of the association between bullying and substance use. A study from Shifa et al. (2025) revealed that being male, having a single marital status, a family history of substance use, low perceived social support, and the presence of mental health conditions were associated with an increased likelihood of substance use. Samara et al. (2021) also found that a positive parent-child relationship acted as a protective factor, moderating the correlation between problematic internet use and substance abuse, as well as between problematic internet use and traditional bullying.

General Strain Theory (GST) explain why bullied adolescent students may have higher rates of substance use. This theory proposes that deviant behaviour may be an alternative way for individuals experiencing strain usually as a form of social pressures, which explains why substance use may be more likely among adolescents who have experienced strain through bullying victimization. Agnew (1992) presents three major types of strain which may influence adolescent towards substance use as a result of poor relationships with others. The three types of strain exist when: a) other individuals prevent one from reaching goals that are positively valued, b) threaten to remove or remove positively valued stimuli possessed by the individual, c) present the individual with negatively valued stimuli (Agnew, 1992). Bullying victimization is a major type of strain that present individual in various form such as; verbal; nasty teasing and name calling; physical such as harm, property damage or theft; threatening such as intimidation or coercion; relational such as social exclusion or friendship manipulation; social such as spreading lies or false rumour (Shaw et al., 2013). Adolescent may attempt to escape from the victimization (resulting in truancy), terminate or seek revenge against the source of aggression, or manage the negative effect of the victimization by using substances.

Agnew also provided a rationale for why adolescents may choose one mode of adaption over another as well as why only some adolescents may engage in perpetrating others. Agnew proposed three types of coping mechanisms: cognitive, behavioural, and emotional (Agnew, 1992). Cognitive coping occurs when an adolescent attempts to minimize or deny their negative feelings. An example of cognitive coping would be when an individual states “It does not matter,” or “I am better off anyway,” (Agnew, 1992). Behavioural coping takes place when an adolescent takes action to permanently solve the perceived cause of their negative feelings (Agnew, 1992). Behavioural coping could result to indulging with friends using substances, or result in victimizing other in return. Emotional coping occurs when an adolescent does not seek to deny or solve their negative feelings, but only reduce their negative emotions. Adolescents might choose exercise, go out with friends, or indulge in substances. Building on stress-buffering theory which posit that students who are victims of bullying receive social support, that social support may buffer them from negative outcomes, such as anxiety, depression, and substance use. The main-effect model advocates that social support has a positive benefit for all children and adolescents (Cohen et al., 2000; Cohen & Wills, 1985), regardless of stress levels or circumstances. Lack of social support amidst bullying incident can lead to negative emotions like unhappiness, depression, and anxiety, increasing the risk for substance use among adolescent students. Social support taking various forms, including affective support (love, liking, and respect), instrumental support (aid in school

work, information, or money), emotional support (warmth, nurturance, and reassurance), appraisal support, and informational support (Rueger & Johnson, 2024), can play a significant role in ameliorating the suspected association of bullying with substance use among adolescents. This is because, with its stress buffering strength, adolescents can find it easy to cope with life stressors, reducing bullying strain that may lead to substance use.

While the literature has provided valuable insights into these associations of bullying with substance use, this study identified substantial gaps in the existing research: (a) knowledge gap: there is dearth of studies that offer comprehensive moderating roles of social support in the association of peer bullying with substance use; (b) population gap: a significant gap was identified addressing adolescent students in the eastern part of Nigeria especially Ebonyi state precisely. Notably, the population of adolescent students in Eastern part of Nigeria have not been systematically examined stressing that the findings from Western Countries and other parts of Nigeria may not be directly applicable to this group of population. To address all these gaps, this study explores the role of perceived social support in the association of peer bullying with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki using a quantitative research approach.

Problem statement

The recent composite local arrest from the national drug law enforcement agency in Ebonyi state caught up the interest of this research study. Between January and March 2025, there occurred a seizure of 55.947 kilogrammes of illicit substances and arrest of 112 suspects (85 males and 27 females aged between 16 and 76). According to report, the seized drugs comprised 43.582kg of cannabis sativa, 0.004kg of tramadol tablets, 0.400kg of tramadol 1000mg (1,189 capsules) and 0.207kg of diazepam (988 tablets), 11.2kg of monkey tail, 0.054kg of methamphetamine, and 0.020kg of bromazepam (46 tablets), 0.244kg of pentazocine (84 capsules) and 0.014kg of heroin were recovered during the operation (Ogar, 2025). The seized drugs weighed 55.947 kilogrammes including other assorted psychotropic substances. This incidence confirmed the alarming rate of substance use particularly in this part of country presenting a significant public health issue.

Considering the fact that early initiation of substance begins at adolescents' stage (Obadeji, 2020), it then calls for early intervention from all stake holders and researchers for strategic solution. This is because the consequences are not only affecting the society but as a result may hinder academic growth of this group of population under study. Thus, thus present research aims to explore the strength of association of bullying with substance use. By examining this relationship in-dept, this study may likely find that adolescents who experience higher levels of peer bullying, are significantly more likely to engage in substance use as a coping mechanism.

In other hand, social support from family, friend and significant others is a social variable suspected to be a viable factor capable of meddling the strength of association of bullying with substance use. In that, it may stand as a catalyst between the association, this study could find that perceived social support from peers, family, and significant others may moderate the relationship between bullying experiences and substance use, emphasizing the point that adolescents with higher perceived social support might be less likely to use substances, even if they experience peer bullying. This finding would emphasize the need of social support networks in mitigating the negative effects of bullying on substance use. It would underscore the importance of fostering strong supportive relationships within families, peer groups, and communities as a preventive measure against substance use. This contribution would inform social interventions aimed at strengthening social bonds to protect adolescents from harmful social behaviours like substance use. Hence, this study aims to provide answers to the following research questions.

Research questions

1. Would bullying be significantly associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki?
2. Would social support from families, friends, significant others be significantly associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki?
3. Would social support from families, friends and significant others be significantly moderate the association of bullying with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki?

The present study

This study sought to investigate the moderating role of social support in the association between bullying with substance use. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Determine if bullying would be associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.
2. Examine if social support from families, friends, and significant others would be associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.
3. Assess if support from families, friends, significant others would moderate the association of bullying with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual model illustrating the moderating roles of variables 'a', in the relationship between 'b' with 'c'

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the role perceived social support in the association between peer bullying with substance use.

The above framework explained the roles of perceived social support on the association of peer bullying with substance use among adolescent students. By examining these relationships in-

depth, this study would contribute to the existing body of knowledge and provide valuable insights for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies to adolescents' risky-behaviours.

Hypothesis

1. Bullying would be associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.
2. Social support from families, friends and significant others would be associated with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.
3. Support from families, friends and significant others would moderate the association of bullying with substance use among adolescent students in Abakaliki.

Method

This study investigated the role of perceived social support in the association of peer bullying with substance use. Using systematic sampling technique, the list of the selected government-run secondary schools used were proportionally arrived based on odd nth values in the distribution list after arranging the school names in alphabetical order; and stratified sampling techniques were used to sample 375 adolescent students from different strata of classes from class level 1 to class level 6. The population of the study comprise public secondary school from Abakaliki local government area in Abakaliki education zone. Data was gathered using the following instrument: the psychoactive substance use questionnaire (PSUQ) by Eze, (2006); the forms of bullying scale (FBS) by (Shaw et al., 2013); and the multidimensional scale of perceived social support (MSPP) (Zimet et al., 1988). To achieve this objective, an introductory letter was used to obtain permission and consent from the principals of the schools selected for the study. All the copies of the questionnaire were distributed and collected physically. The design used were cross sectional design and statistical analysis used was regression-based Hayes PROCESS macro version 4.0 for SPSS version 28 to test the hypotheses.

Result

Table 1:

Pearson's correlations of demographic factors, Peer bullying (bullying and perpetration), and social support (family, friends, sig. others) and substance use among adolescent students.

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Age	16.00	1.50	-.10						
2. Bullied	18.64	8.19	.04	.09					
3. Perpetrator	15.40	7.02	-.02	.13	.46				
4. Family support	17.73	8.87	.03	-.03	-.01	-.07			
5. Friends support	11.68	6.08	-.05	-.06	-.06	-.07	.79		
6. Sig. others support	17.02		8.75	.79	.39	.85	.55	.00	.00
7. Substance use	5.95	6.01	-.04	.21	.25	.21	-.02	-.10	-.03

The correlation table above evidenced that bullied and perpetrator positively associated with substance use ($r = .09, p < .05$; $r = .46, p < .05$) respectively. Family support was negatively associated with substance use ($r = -.07, p < .05$). Friends support was associated with substance use ($r = .79, p < .05$). The demographic variable of age was negatively associated with substance use ($r = -.10, p < .05$).

Table 2: Hierarchical multiple regression results for test of the moderating roles of social support in the associations of peer bullying with substance use

Predictors	Step 1		Step 2		Step 3		Step 4		Step 5		Step 6	
	β	<i>t</i>	β	<i>t</i>	β	<i>t</i>	B	<i>T</i>	β	<i>t</i>	B	<i>T</i>
Gender	.05	-0.91	.024	-0.466	.033	-0.651	.046	-0.915	.047	-0.925	.041	-0.810
Ethnic group	.03	-0.52	.043	-0.688	.042	-0.697	.038	-0.629	.039	-0.639	.033	-0.545
Religion	.09	1.4	.073	1.164	.073	1.187	.068	1.099	.068	1.101	.066	1.064
Age			.199	3.879	.168	3.344	.162	3.212	.159	3.134	.152	2.981
Bullied Perpetrator					.181	3.250	.169	3.039	.152	1.212	.058	.418
Family support					.108	1.944	.112	1.997	.110	1.945	.282	2.270
Friends support							.137	1.131	.007	-0.022	.109	-0.296
Sig. others support									.184	2.178	.182	-0.846
Bullied x family support									.013	.106	.139	.441
Bullied x friends support											.218	.530
Bullied x sig. others support											.189	.425
Perpetrator x family support											.002	-0.009
Perpetrator x friends support											.193	-0.441
Perpetrator x sig. others support											.121	-0.271
											.169	.383
											.138	-0.409
											.315	-0.698

** $p < .05$ ** $p < .01$ ***

Table two above are result of the hierarchical multiple regressions after controlling for gender, ethnic group, religion, and age.

In step 1 of the model, religion among ethnic group and gender was positively associated with substance use ($\beta = .09, t = 1.04, p < .05$). The model was significant, $\Delta F(3,371) = .86, p < .05$. This accounted for 5% of the variance in substance use.

In step 2, Age was added and it was positively associated with substance use ($\beta = .20, t = 3.88, p < .05$). it accounted for 2% of the variance in substance use.

In step 3, bullied perpetrator was positively associated with substance use ($\beta = .18, t = 3.25, p < .05; \beta = .11, t = 1.94, p < .05$) respectively. The model was significant $\Delta F(2,368) = 12.61, p < .05$. Bullied perpetrator accounted for 10% of the variance in substance use.

In step 4, family, friends and sig. others supports was added to the model, family, and sig. others support was positively associated with substance use ($\beta = .14, t = 1.13, p < .05; \beta = .01, t = .12$) respectively. The model was significant $\Delta F(3,37) = 1.69, p < .05$. it accounted for 2% of the variance in substance use.

In step 5, the interaction of bullied with family, friends and sig. others supports were added to the model. The interaction term for bullied and family support was associated with substance use ($\beta = .23, t = .53, p < .05$). The model was significant $\Delta F(3,36) = .10, p < .05$. It accounted for 2% variance in substance use indicating that family support moderated the association of bullying with substance use.

In step 6, the interaction term for perpetrator and family, friends, significant others were added. Only family support was associated with substance use ($\beta = .17, t = .38, p < .05$). The model was significant $\Delta F(3,36) = .98, p < .05$, accounting for 2% variance in substance use. It indicates that family support moderated the association of perpetrator and substance use suggesting the need for strong family bond as a social mechanism to substance use among adolescents.

Discussion

The correlation analysis evidenced that bullied and perpetrator were positively associated with substance use ($r = .09, p < .05$; $r = .46, p < .05$) respectively. This finding confirmed the first hypothesis which stated that bullying would significantly be associated with substance use. The finding is in line with that of Gaete, et al. (2017); Airagnes et al. (2023); and Jiexin and Zigiang (2024) whose findings indicated positive association of bullying with substance use. The present study revealed that experience of bullying was significantly associated with substance use explaining general strain theory which proposed that individuals experiencing strain usually as a form of social pressure take action to permanently solve the perceived cause of their negative feelings (Agnew, 1992), which explains why substance use becomes the social mechanism to such experience.

Secondly, family support was negatively associated with substance use ($r = -.07, p < .05$). Friends support was associated with substance use ($r = .79, p < .05$). There is dearth of research studies based on this evidence to support this area. This signified a gap in knowledge addressing these variables. Thus, this study confirmed the second hypothesis stating that friends not family and significant others' support would positively be associated with substance use. Demographic variable of age was negatively associated with substance use ($r = -.10, p < .05$).

The third hypotheses which stated that support from families, friends and significant others would significantly moderate the association of bullying with substance use was tested. Family, and significant others' support was found to positively moderate the association ($\beta = .14, t = 1.13, p < .05$; $\beta = .01, t = .12$) respectively for bullied. For perpetrator, only family support moderated the association of perpetrator and substance use suggesting the need to foster strong family support. This is in consistent with the study of Samara et al. (2021) whose finding indicated a positive parent-child relationship moderating traditional bullying and substance use. It suggests that supportive family addresses personal and social problems, and can address critical issues like bullying and substance use. The main-effect model presumes that access to social support improves one's overall psychological state (e.g., sense of worth and belonging, security, stability) and may provide the individual with support, which in turn reduces psychological problems (Cohen et al., 2000). Thus, this finding has proved that family, not friends and significant others is a good viable social catalyst for bullying and substance use.

Implication of the finding

This study significantly advances our understanding of the social mechanisms that contribute to substance use. It highlights the importance of addressing bullying in social settings like schools and communities to prevent substance use. The insight is informative to policy makers and education programmes aimed at creating healthier social environment for adolescent students.

Policymakers and educators can leverage findings to improve supportive relationships within families as a preventive measure against substance use. This would inform social

interventions aimed at strengthening social bonds to protect adolescents from harmful social behaviour. This study underscores the protective potential of family support among adolescent students, demonstrating that it is not only a solution to control bullying behaviour but also a catalyst for substance use prevention.

Limitation/Further research

This study has actually investigated how social support from different dimensions (family, friends and significant others) can serve as a moderator in the association of bullying and substance use using qualitative approach with a sample of 375 in three public secondary schools. Further research should endeavour to extend the number of schools to accommodate more population of adolescent students. Adding private secondary schools would also help to assess contributions of support from friends and significant others' moderating strength.

Recommendation

1. This study identified the significant role of family bond in fostering protective measure in adolescents' wellbeing, it is recommended that parent teachers association meetings in secondary education should encourage families to leverage on this finding so to mitigate the harmful social behaviour of substance use among their adolescent children.
2. Recognizing that bullying is a cause leading to substance use as indicated in this finding, it is recommended that education policies and programmes should inculcate in their policies fines against perpetrators such as sanction, suspension and extortion in other to build fear on that and prevent such harmful and distressing behaviour among adolescents in schools.

Summary/conclusion

Substance use has gradually become endemic among adolescents. The mean score discovered in this study indicated the extent of its usage among secondary school student. Due to its harmful effect, it becomes a clarion attention from all stake holders. Bullying as discovered from this study has strong association accounting for almost 10 percent contribution to substance use. Bullying is found through literature as being rampant in secondary schools. There is need to curb out this social phenomenon accounting for substance use. This study explores the critical role of social support from family, friends, and significant others in the association of bullying with substance use. It was discovered that support from family play vital role in controlling the prevalence of these two factors. Hence, this study view support from family as a catalyst for substance use among adolescent students.

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